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**E5.6.1 Final design of high precision
smart telemetry for 6G optimisation 1.1**
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PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
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List of Acronyms

6G	Sixth Generation
API	Application Programming Interface
B5G	Beyond 5G
CoAP	Constrained Application Protocol
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
Feast	Feature Store for Machine Learning
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IoT	Internet of Things
Jaeger	Open Source, End-to-End Distributed Tracing
mL	Machine Learning
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
PostgreSQL	Open Source Relational Database
Prometheus	Open Source Monitoring and Alerting Toolkit
QoS	Quality of Service
Redis	Remote Dictionary Server
SDK	Software Development Kit
SP	Specific Project (used in document IDs)
Telegraf	Open Source Server Agent for Collecting Metrics
TM Forum	Telecom Management Forum
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications
UI	User Interface

Table 1 Acronyms

1. Executive Overview

As part of the 6GENABLERS project, this paper is the result of considerable research and design efforts targeted at creating a high-precision telemetry system customized for 6G networks. The final design is a major improvement over earlier versions and sets a new standard in telemetry technology. It is based on fundamental research reported in **6GENABLERS-SP1-L3-P5-A5.1** and following early design efforts in **6GENABLERS-SP1-L3-P5-E5.2.1**.

The proposed design integrates cutting-edge advancements in telemetry to provide an accuracy and efficiency architecture design to try to support the demands of 6G networking. The document details the evolution from the initial design to the final, more sophisticated model, highlighting the rationale behind pivotal design choices and modifications. These changes are rooted deeply in the project's initial findings and are aligned with the system requirements outlined in **6GENABLERS-SP1-L3-P2-A2.4**, ensuring full compatibility and optimization within the proposed 6G network infrastructure.

A key component of this design is its integration with both **OpenTelemetry** and **TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager**, which together enhance its capability to deliver real-time, high-fidelity data analysis and management. This integration covers the current standards, is a great combination for manage the network telemetry standards and will be very useful in 6G networks.

This paper also investigates other possible designs, offering a comprehensive comparison study and supporting the ultimate choice with respect to performance effectiveness, scalability, and resilience to changing network technology. After assessing each option's ability to adhere to the strict specifications of next-generation networks, the design that was selected offered the best compromise between performance and complexity.

The new characteristics of the telemetry system and its predicted influence on the 6G environment are highlighted through a thorough assessment of the enhancements over existing systems, demonstrating progress compared to the state of the art. The complex aspects of the design's interdependencies within the more general 6G architecture indicate its crucial role in the network's overall process.

In conclusion, this design represents a significant leap forward in the development of network systems that can support the high-speed, high-volume, and high-reliability requirements of 6G networks. It not only fulfils the envisioned specifications but also provides a scalable and robust framework that paves the way for future innovations in telecommunications.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose of the Document

This paper describes the completed architecture of a high-precision telemetry system designed to improve the performance of upcoming 6G networks. It functions as a comprehensive blueprint that describes the technical details and subtle architectural features of the suggested design and places its evolution within the larger framework of the 6GENABLERS project. To guarantee compliance with the developing standards of 6G technology, the paper seeks to give stakeholders thorough insights into the design decisions taken, the improvements over earlier prototypes, and the reasoning behind these choices.

2.2 Scope and Objectives

The scope of this document encompasses the presentation of a finalized design for a telemetry system that can deliver high-precision monitoring and data analytics in a 6G environment. Objectives of the document include:

- **Detailed Design Presentation:** To outline the architectural specifics and operational dynamics of the telemetry system, providing a clear understanding of its functionality and integration capabilities within 6G infrastructures.
- **Design Justification:** To justify the selected design over other alternatives through comparative analysis, focusing on its superior efficacy and alignment with system requirements.
- **State of the Art Advancement:** To demonstrate how the design advances the current state of the art in telemetry technology, offering innovations that enhance data accuracy, processing speed, and system scalability.
- **Project Alignment:** To ensure that the design is in full harmony with the goals and objectives of the 6GENABLERS project, contributing to the overarching aim of optimizing network performance and reliability.

2.3 Relationship to 6GENABLERS Project Goals

The 6GENABLERS project is dedicated to spearheading advancements in 6G technology, with a focus on creating solutions that are scalable, efficient, and capable of supporting the high demands of future network environments. This document and the design it proposes are integral to this mission. The telemetry system design is crafted to meet the project's strict requirements for precision, efficiency, and adaptability, thus directly contributing to the following specific project goals:

- **Enhancing Network Efficiency:** By providing precise and real-time data analytics, the telemetry system improves decision-making processes, thereby enhancing the overall efficiency of 6G networks.
- **Supporting Scalable Solutions:** The design incorporates scalable architecture that can adapt to increasing demands without compromising performance, aligning with the project's emphasis on future-proof technologies.

- **Advancing Technological Frontiers:** By integrating the latest advancements in telemetry and performance management, the design pushes the technological limits, setting new benchmarks for what can be achieved in next-generation network monitoring.

In conclusion, this document encapsulates the culmination of extensive research and iterative design processes that epitomize the collaborative spirit and innovative aspirations of the 6GENABLERS project. It represents the base for implementing a telemetry system that will not only meet but exceed the expectations for 6G network performance, thus setting a new standard for network management technologies.

3. System Requirements Review

3.1 System Requirements as Defined in 6GENABLERS-SP1-L3-P2-A2.4

The initial system requirements outlined in deliverable 6GENABLERS-SP1-L3-P2-A2.4 set the foundation for developing high-precision telemetry systems tailored for 6G networks. These requirements were designed to address both functional and non-functional aspects necessary for the seamless operation and integration of telemetry within advanced mobile networks. Key requirements included:

- **High Bandwidth and Low Latency:** Essential for supporting real-time data collection and processing, facilitating immediate response capabilities and high data throughput essential for 6G applications.
- **Scalability:** The system must efficiently handle different scales of network demand without degradation in performance, adapting dynamically to the number of devices and the volume of data traffic.
- **Fault Tolerance and Reliability:** Ensuring continuous operation without service interruptions, even in the event of partial system failures.
- **Data Accuracy and Precision:** High fidelity in data collection and analysis to enable precise monitoring and management of network resources.
- **Security and Privacy Compliance:** Robust encryption and secure data handling processes to protect user data and ensure compliance with international data protection regulations.

These requirements form the most important points of the system's capabilities, ensuring that it not only supports the technological demands of next-generation networks but also adheres to strict performance standards.¹

3.2 Overview of Telemetry Needs and Challenges in 6G Networks

Telemetry in 6G networks is pivotal for enabling advanced applications like holoportation, autonomous vehicles, and IoT on a massive scale. The shift to 6G introduces new dynamics and challenges that must be addressed to fully leverage its potential:

- **Ultra-Low Latency:** 6G aims to drastically reduce latency to under one millisecond, which requires telemetry systems capable of operating and making decisions at unprecedented speeds.
- **Increased Network Density:** With significantly more devices per square kilometer than current networks, 6G will challenge telemetry systems to

¹ G.B., Alberto (Oct. 2023). *6GENABLERS_E2.4_Report on requirements for high-precision smart telemetry*. I2CAT.

manage and analyze data from potentially millions of endpoints without latency or errors.

- **Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) and Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC):** These key 6G services demand robust telemetry to ensure service quality and reliability, requiring comprehensive data capture and real-time processing.
- **Network Slicing:** As 6G will support customized virtual networks (slices) for different needs, telemetry must be able to manage and monitor performance across potentially thousands of independent slices simultaneously.
- **Dynamic Network Adaptation:** With 6G networks expected to be highly adaptable to changing conditions and demands, telemetry systems must be equally flexible, capable of dynamic self-configuration, self-optimization, and real-time problem resolution.

These challenges underscore the need for a sophisticated telemetry system that is not only highly responsive and adaptable but also capable of handling the complexity and volume of data intrinsic to 6G networks. The design proposed in this document aims to address these challenges by advancing the state of the art in telemetry technology and providing a robust framework for its deployment in next-generation mobile networks.

4. Initial Design Overview

4.1 Description of the Initial Design from 6GENABLERS-SP1-L3-P5-E5.2.1

The Figure 1 represent the architecture including key components, each of which plays a crucial role in ensuring the efficient deployment and operation of the entire system.

Figure 1. Complete System Architecture in Initial Design

The initial design outlined in 6GENABLERS-SP1-L3-P5-E5.2.1 provided a comprehensive blueprint for developing high-precision telemetry systems for 6G networks. This design was conceptualized to enable the robust collection, processing, and analysis of telemetry data across highly dynamic and scalable 6G infrastructures. Key components of this initial design included:

- OpenTelemetry Integration:** Utilizing OpenTelemetry to standardize telemetry data collection across diverse network devices and services. This integration aimed to facilitate seamless observability and operational analytics.

- **TM Forum Interfaces:** Implementing TM Forum standards to ensure that the telemetry system aligns with global performance management benchmarks and quality of service requirements.
- **Modular Architecture:** A scalable, modular design that allows for easy adaptation and expansion as network technologies evolve or as new requirements emerge.
- **Edge Computing Capabilities:** Incorporating edge computing to handle data processing locally at the network edge, reducing latency and bandwidth use while enhancing data processing speed and reliability.
- **AI-Driven Analytics:** Leveraging artificial intelligence to enhance data analysis capabilities, enabling predictive maintenance, anomaly detection, and real-time decision-making.

These elements were designed to work cohesively to provide a scalable, flexible, and robust telemetry framework that could support the advanced capabilities expected of 6G networks, including ultra-low latency, massive device connectivity, and high reliability.²

4.2 Summary of Design Objectives and Key Features

The primary objectives of the initial design were to:

1. **Enhance Real-Time Capabilities:** Enable the telemetry system to process and respond to data in real-time, a critical requirement for supporting URLLC applications in 6G networks.
2. **Support Massive Scalability:** Ensure that the telemetry system can scale efficiently to handle the increased device density and data volumes associated with 6G networks.
3. **Provide Comprehensive Observability:** Offer deep insights into network performance and user experiences to optimize network management and service delivery.
4. **Enable Dynamic Adaptability:** Allow the system to dynamically adjust to changing network conditions and user demands without manual intervention.
5. **Assure Security and Compliance:** Integrate robust security measures to protect telemetry data and ensure compliance with international data protection regulations.

² Chen, D. Gao, C. H. Foh and H. Yan, "CFINT: Cluster Based Fast In-band Network-wide Telemetry in 6G-enabled Networks," 2022 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 2022, pp. 1699-1704, doi: 10.1109/GCWkshps56602.2022.10008610.

Key features designed to meet these objectives included:

- **Distributed Data Collection:** Utilizing a network of distributed collectors to gather data from a wide array of sources without overwhelming any single point in the system.³
- **Advanced Data Processing Engines:** Employing sophisticated data processing algorithms that can analyze large volumes of data quickly and accurately.⁴
- **Real-Time Data Analytics:** Implementing real-time analytics to turn telemetry data into actionable insights almost instantaneously.
- **Flexible Data Integration:** Providing capabilities to integrate with various data sources and formats to ensure comprehensive network visibility.
- **Security Protocols:** Implementing end-to-end encryption, access controls, and continuous monitoring to safeguard data integrity and privacy.

This initial design set the stage for a telemetry system that not only meets the current expectations from a 6G infrastructure but also provides a robust foundation for future enhancements as network requirements evolve.

³ G.B., Alberto (Dec. 2023). *6GENABLERS_E5.2.1_Initial design of high precision smart telemetry for 6G optimisation*. I2CAT.

⁴ Kholidy, Hisham A. and Mohammed Abuzamak. "5G Network Management, Orchestration, and Architecture: A Practical Study of the MonB5G project." ArXiv abs/2212.13747 (2022): n. pag.

5. Final Design Description

The final design for the high-precision telemetry enablement in 6G networks integrates a sophisticated array of technologies and methodologies designed to optimize telemetry data processing. This section offers a detailed view of the architecture, including diagrams and component descriptions, along with an explanation of how the design meets the project's system requirements.

5.1 Detailed Description of the Proposed Final Design

The design architecture is built to handle massive, heterogeneous data flows typical in 6G environments, ensuring data is captured, processed, and analyzed efficiently to support real-time decision-making and network optimization. It leverages a suite of components each tailored to specific aspects of telemetry processing: data collection, normalization, feature extraction, and data analysis.

5.2 Detailed Component and Workflow Descriptions

Figure 2. Detailed Components of the Final Design.

Figure 2 represents the detailed components of the telemetry system:

- **Telemetry Sources:** These are the sensors and devices throughout the network that generate diverse data such as metrics, logs, and traces, essential for network monitoring and management.
- **OpenTelemetry Collector:** Serves as the entry point for data collection, standardizing, and buffering incoming data to manage loads and prepare it for advanced processing.
- **Telegraf:**
 - **Data Collection Agent:** Telegraf operates as a plugin-driven server agent for collecting and sending statistics and metrics. It is configured to receive metrics, logs, and traces from the OpenTelemetry Collector.
 - **Metrics Processing:** After receiving the data, Telegraf processes it to conform to InfluxDB's data format, enhancing the data's structure and ensuring that it is ready for efficient querying and analysis.
 - **Data Transmission:** Telegraf then sends this processed data to InfluxDB, where it is stored as time-series data. This integration is crucial for maintaining a high-performance data analysis environment that supports real-time monitoring and historical data analysis.
- **Telemetry Fusion Hub:** This component consolidates data from various collectors, ensuring initial data coherence and preliminary checks before sending to the centralized hub.

- **Centralized Collector Hub:** Further validates and checks the integrity of data from the Fusion Hub, acting as a central point for quality assurance before data proceeds to feature extraction.
- **Feature Services:** Implements tools like Feast for extracting and managing data features, crucial for detailed analysis. It utilizes Redis for real-time data access and PostgreSQL for historical and batch data processing, helpful different analytical needs.
- **Alarm Services:**
 - **Functionality:** These services proactively scan the telemetry data for anomalies and faults, using defined metrics and patterns. If an issue is detected, the system automatically initiates protocols to address the issue, aiming to minimize network downtime and improve reliability.
 - **TM Forum Alarm API:** This API is integrated to manage the lifecycle of alarms, from creation through clearance. It facilitates real-time alerts and automates the resolution processes, thereby ensuring swift responses to potential disruptions.
- **Analytics Services:**
 - **Performance Monitoring:** Utilizes advanced data analysis techniques to continuously monitor the health and performance of network elements. This includes assessing system load, resource utilization, and traffic patterns to try to avoid the bottlenecks.
 - **Quality of Service Optimization:** Adheres to TM Forum's standards to dynamically manage QoS parameters. This ensures that the network services meet the expected performance levels under varying load conditions.
 - **End-User Experience Enhancement:** Focuses on optimizing the network's performance from the end-user's perspective. This involves adjusting network settings in real-time to enhance service delivery and user satisfaction.
 - **TM Forum Quality of Service API:** Integrated to facilitate the configuration and management of service quality standards, enabling the system to maintain and adjust QoS levels automatically based on real-time network data and user demands.
- **Business Applications:** These are applications that utilize the processed data to optimize network operations, including resource management and predictive maintenance.
- **User Interfaces (UI):** The primary interfaces for visualizing the data and insights derived from the system. These interfaces include:
 - **Grafana:** Used for creating dashboards that visualize the metrics, logs, and traces managed by Prometheus and Jaeger. It allows users to visually monitor network health and performance in real-time.

- **Prometheus:** Provides monitoring and alerting for network operations, collecting and processing metrics from the OpenTelemetry Collector and other sources within the network.
- **Jaeger:** Utilized for tracing and analyzing the flow of requests and data through the network, helping to pinpoint issues and optimize performance.

Figure 3 shows the complete workflow, including all components and subcomponents of the telemetry system:

Figure 3. Detailed Description of the Proposed Final Design

5.3 Detailed Component Analysis

5.3.1 OpenTelemetry Collector Integration

The OpenTelemetry Collector is pivotal in this architecture, serving as the main conduit through which all telemetry data—metrics, traces, and logs—is collected, processed, and exported. It is crucial for standardizing telemetry data across services, especially

those deployed on Kubernetes, ensuring consistent data formats and reliable metrics for downstream processing.

- **Collector Functionality:** It standardizes telemetry data, ensuring compatibility and efficient processing downstream.
- **Integration Points:** The Collector feeds into both the Telemetry Fusion Hub and the Centralized Collector Hub, providing a primary data source that prepares diverse telemetry inputs for further processing.

5.3.2 Protocol-Specific Collectors

5.3.2.1 Workflow and Technologies:

- **Data Capture:** Specifically designed for MQTT, CoAP, and HTTP protocols, these collectors are fundamental to standardizing incoming telemetry data into a universally compatible format (primarily JSON).
- **Connection Management:** Maintains robust and fault-tolerant data ingestion using OpenTelemetry SDKs to manage multiple concurrent data streams.
- **Buffering Mechanism:** Utilizes Redis to buffer data during peak loads, ensuring data integrity and continuity.

Figure 4. Protocol-Specific Collectors Workflow

5.3.2.2 Detailed Component Functions and Technologies

Component	Technology Used	Function
Telemetry Source	MQTT, CoAP, HTTP	Sources of data employing different communication protocols, adjusted for real-time data collection.
OpenTelemetry Collector	OpenTelemetry	Central node for initial data capture, responsible for standardizing protocol-specific data into a common format.
Connection Manager	OpenTelemetry SDKs	Manages robust, fault-tolerant connections for multiple data streams, ensuring continuous data flow.
Redis Buffer	Redis	Buffers data during peak loads to prevent loss and maintain continuity; acts as a temporary storage.

Data Normalization	Python with FastAPI	Converts incoming data to JSON format for uniform processing and integration into the telemetry pipeline.
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Table 2. Detailed Component Functions and Technologies

5.3.3 Centralized Collector Hub and Feature Services

5.3.3.1 Integration and Data Flow:

- **Telemetry Fusion Hub:** Aggregates processed data from various collectors, including the OpenTelemetry Collector, ensuring efficient data handling and preparation for feature extraction and analysis.
- **Data Integrity Validator:** Prior to forwarding for feature extraction, the data undergoes validation checks to ensure accuracy and completeness.
- **Unified Data Distributor:** Manages the distribution of validated data to downstream services such as Feature Services and Analytics Services, ensuring timely and balanced data flow.

Figure 5. Data Flow in Final Design.

5.3.3.2 Component Descriptions and Functions

Component	Function	Description
OpenTelemetry Collector	Data Collection and Normalization	Primary entry point for telemetry data; it aggregates and normalizes data for consistent processing downstream.
Telemetry	Aggregation	Central node that collects normalized data,

Fusion Hub		ensuring efficient handling and preparation for validation and analysis.
Data Integrity Validator	Validation	Performs extensive checks on aggregated data to confirm accuracy and completeness, ensuring that downstream processes receive error-free information.
Unified Data Distributor	Data Distribution	Manages the routing of validated data to necessary services, balancing and timing the flow to Feature Services and Analytics Services.
Feature Services	Feature Extraction and Management	Processes validated data to extract and manage features critical for machine learning models, ensuring features are stored and accessible.
Analytics Services	Data Analysis	Performs in-depth analysis on the data to derive actionable insights, feeding these insights into business applications for strategic decisions.

Table 3. Component Descriptions and Functions

5.3.4 Feature Services (Feast)

5.3.4.1 Functionality and Integration:

- **Feature Extraction:** Manages the extraction of significant features from processed telemetry data, crucial for machine learning applications, using Feast for lifecycle management.
- **Feature Storage:** Combines Redis for real-time access and PostgreSQL for batch processing and long-term storage, optimizing feature management.
- **Workflow Automation:** Employs Apache Airflow to automate data flows from collection through to feature extraction, ensuring efficient operations.

Figure 6. Feature Services Workflow

5.3.4.2 Detailed Workflow Description

Stage	Technology	Description
Data Normalization	OpenTelemetry	Aligns incoming telemetry data into a standardized format to ensure consistency and compatibility for feature extraction.
Feature Extraction	Feast	Manages the extraction of significant features from the normalized data, crucial for enhancing machine learning models and analytical processes.
Feature Lifecycle Management	Feast	Oversees the management of feature versions, updates, and retrievals, ensuring that all feature sets are current and consistent across different applications.
Real-Time Access	Redis	Provides immediate access to features for real-time applications, utilizing high-speed in-memory data storage to facilitate dynamic data retrieval.
Batch Processing & Long-term Storage	PostgreSQL	Ensures the efficient handling of batch processes and long-term data storage needs, offering robust database management for non-immediate but critical data retrieval.
Workflow Automation	Apache Airflow	Automates the sequence of data processing tasks from collection to feature storage, ensuring efficient, consistent, and error-free operations across the data pipeline.

Table 4. Detailed Workflow Description

5.3.5 Component Integration and Technology Usage

The following table outlines the essential components and subcomponents of the high-precision telemetry enablement system designed for 6G networks. It specifies the technologies employed and the functions these components perform within the architecture. This comprehensive breakdown helps elucidate the role of each technology in facilitating the collection, processing, and analysis of telemetry data, which is pivotal for optimizing network operations and machine learning processes. The architecture is designed to be robust and scalable, ensuring high data integrity and system performance through meticulous data management and processing strategies.

Component	Subcomponent	Technology Used	Function
Protocol-Specific Collectors	Data Capture, Connection Management, Buffering	OpenTelemetry, Redis	Standardize and buffer data for efficiency
Data Format Collectors	Parsing, Normalization, Error Handling	OpenTelemetry, Prometheus	Parse and standardize formats, handle errors
Centralized Collector Hub	Telemetry Fusion Hub, Data Integrity Validator, Unified Data Distributor	OpenTelemetry, Custom Validation Tools	Aggregate and validate data, manage distribution
Feature	Feature Extraction,	Feast, Redis,	Manage features for

Services	Feature Storage	PostgreSQL	machine learning readiness
Analytics Services	Data Analysis	Custom Analytical Tools, TM Forum APIs	Generate insights from processed data
Telegraf	Data Ingestion	Telegraf	Facilitate data flow from OpenTelemetry to InfluxDB
OpenTelemetry Collector	Data Collection, Processing, Export	OpenTelemetry	Collect, process, and export telemetry data
Kubernetes	Container Orchestration	Kubernetes	Deploy and manage components in a productive environment

Table 5. Component Integration and Technology Usage

5.3.6 Integration with OpenNebula's Monitoring Systems

In the final design of our high-precision telemetry system for 6G networks, special attention has been given to ensure seamless integration with third-party orchestration platforms such as OpenNebula. Recognizing the importance of versatile and robust data acquisition capabilities, our design extensively supports OpenTelemetry, Prometheus, and InfluxDB, facilitating a wide range of data collection possibilities suited for diverse network environments managed by OpenNebula as outlined in their recent report (6GENABLERS_SP1_E4.3.1 - Initial Design of Smart Resource Interconnection⁵).

5.3.6.1 OpenTelemetry SDK Integration

Our telemetry system's core component is the OpenTelemetry SDK. This framework is critical for standardizing telemetry data collection across various sources and services. By integrating OpenTelemetry, we empower OpenNebula and other third-party systems to employ this SDK in their components, allowing them to send customized metrics directly to our telemetry system. This setup not only enhances data accuracy and granularity but also ensures that data from OpenNebula's dynamically managed Kubernetes clusters and other edge computing resources are meticulously captured and available for real-time processing, as emphasized in their focus on intelligent orchestration processes (6GENABLERS_SP1_E4.3.1).

5.3.6.2 Utilizing Prometheus and InfluxDB

Apart from OpenTelemetry, our system is equipped to aggregate and analyze metrics from Prometheus and InfluxDB. These tools are renowned for their efficiency in handling time-series data, which is essential for monitoring the performance and health of network infrastructures. By facilitating data ingestion from these platforms, we ensure that OpenNebula can leverage its existing monitoring setups to feed into our telemetry system without requiring extensive modifications. The flexibility of our system to interface with these diverse data sources underscores our commitment to providing a robust, scalable, and forward-compatible monitoring solution, essential for the next generation of network management.

5.3.6.3 Conclusion

By incorporating OpenTelemetry, Prometheus, and InfluxDB into the telemetry system's architecture, we ensure comprehensive coverage and compatibility with

⁵ OpenNebula Systems (Mar. 2024). 6GENABLERS_E 4.3.1_ Initial Design of Smart Resource Interconnection. I2CAT.

OpenNebula's orchestration needs. This strategic integration not only streamlines operations but also enhances the predictive and proactive management capabilities essential for zero-touch deployment and intelligent network orchestration in 6G environments, aligning with the goals set forth in the 6GENABLERS project (6GENABLERS_SP1_E4.3.1).

6. Design Evolution and Rationale

6.1 Overview

The transition from the initial to the final design of the high-precision telemetry enablement for 6G networks has been guided by continuous feedback, rigorous testing, and evolving technological needs. The modifications were targeted to refine and optimize the telemetry processing capabilities, making the system robust and scalable for 6G requirements.

6.2 Evolution of the Design Architecture

The figure 7 illustrates the progression from the initial simplistic architecture, which primarily focused on basic data collection and periodic analysis, to a more comprehensive and integrated approach in the final design. This transition was crucial to accommodate the high volume and velocity of data expected in 6G networks, integrating advanced data processing units like Telegraf and InfluxDB for improved real-time capabilities.

Figure 7. Design Evolution

6.3 Comparison of Initial and Final Designs

This table details the key areas of change between the initial and final designs, emphasizing the strategic enhancements that were necessary to meet the projected needs of 6G networks.

Feature	Initial Design	Final Design	Impact of Change
Data Processing	Basic telemetry collection and processing	Advanced components like Telegraf and InfluxDB	Enhanced real-time processing and data availability
Analytics Services	Generic data analysis framework	Specialized analytics for performance, QoS, and UX	Tailored analytics for specific network and user demands
Feature Services	Basic feature extraction	Advanced feature management with Feast, Redis, PostgreSQL	Support for complex ML applications and adaptive systems
Alarm Services	Basic fault detection	Integrated TM Forum Alarm API for proactive management	Improved network reliability and response time
Telemetry Collection	Broad, unfocused telemetry source integration	Streamlined integration via OpenTelemetry and protocol-specific collectors	Standardized data capture enhancing overall efficiency

Table 6. Comparison of Initial and Final Designs

6.4 Detailed Workflow of Final Design Components

The figure 8 provides a flowchart that maps out the intricate interactions between the newly integrated components such as the Telemetry Fusion Hub, Feature Services, and Analytics Services. It showcases the flow from data collection through processing to actionable insights, highlighting how each component contributes to the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the system.

Figure 8. Detailed Workflow of Final Design Components

6.5 Comparative Analysis of System Architecture Evolution

The transition from the initial to the final design of our high-precision telemetry system for 6G networks marks significant advancements in the architecture's capability to handle the sophisticated demands of modern telecommunications networks. The table below provides a structured comparison of key components, illustrating the improvements made to enhance system efficiency, reliability, and responsiveness.

Component	Previous Version	Final Design	Impact of Evolution
Data Processing	Relied on basic telemetry data collection and periodic analysis.	Incorporates Telegraf for data collection and InfluxDB for data storage, facilitating real-time data	Significantly reduces latency and enhances throughput, enabling immediate real-time insights.

		processing.	
Telemetry Collection	Broad, unfocused telemetry source integration.	Streamlined integration via OpenTelemetry and protocol-specific collectors.	Improves efficiency and completeness of data collection, crucial for accurate network monitoring.
Analytics Services	Generic analytics framework that may not fully cater to the nuanced needs of 6G network environments.	Advanced analytics tailored for performance, QoS, and user experience enhancements.	Allows for more precise insights, leading to better-informed decisions and network optimizations.
Alarm Services	Basic fault detection potentially insufficient for proactive network management.	Advanced alarm services with integrated TM Forum Alarm API for proactive management.	Enhances network reliability and response time by enabling quicker identification and resolution of network issues.
Feature Services	Basic feature extraction without real-time capability.	Integrates Feast for dynamic feature extraction and management using Redis for real-time access and PostgreSQL for historical data.	Facilitates sophisticated machine learning applications and real-time data analysis, enhancing adaptability and responsiveness.
User Interfaces (UI)	Conventional static dashboards.	Use of Grafana for dynamic visualization of metrics, logs, and traces managed by Prometheus and Jaeger.	Provides a more interactive and comprehensive real-time monitoring interface, enhancing user engagement and operational awareness.
Data Integration	Manual data integration processes with limited protocol support.	Automated integration using Telegraf to standardize data ingestion from various protocols into a uniform format.	Streamlines data handling, reduces human error, and increases the system's ability to process diverse data sources efficiently.
Network Management	Periodic manual adjustments based on static reports.	Real-time network management enabled by continuous analytics and telemetry data insights.	Improves network performance and scalability by enabling proactive adjustments and minimizing reactive measures.

Table 7. Comparative Analysis of System Architecture Evolution

Figure 9 represents the difference between the initial and final design in relation to each component.

Figure 9. Comparative Analysis of System Architecture Evolution

6.6 Quantitative Analysis of Telemetry Metrics in Holoportation Services

6.6.1 Overview

This subsection elaborates on the utilization of OpenTelemetry collectors to accurately capture, process, and normalize key performance indicators (KPIs) essential for assessing the quality of holoportation services within 6G networks. Integrating OpenTelemetry enables systematic metric collection and real-time analysis, crucial for upholding the stringent requirements necessary for immersive holoportation experiences.

6.6.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for QoS

As specified by I2CAT for holoportation, the focus is on three primary KPIs critical to the user experience:

1. **Frame Per Second (FPS):** Essential for smooth visual motion, targeting more than 30 FPS for minimal quality and striving for 60 FPS for optimal experiences.
2. **Server-side Perceived Throughput:** Measures the data transmission capacity, crucial for maintaining high-resolution image quality. The expected range is 30 to 50 Mbps (compressed) for standard operations, expanding up to 100 Gbps to 1 Tbps (raw) for delivering ultra-high-definition images.
3. **Frame Delay:** Incorporates both end-to-end latency (< 50–100 ms) and motion-to-photon latency (< 15 ms), critical for real-time interaction synchronization in holoportation, enhancing immersion and reducing user disorientation.

The specific ranges for these KPIs are summarized in the following table:

KPI	Range
Frame per Second (FPS)	> 30 FPS
Server-side perceived throughput per second	30 to 50 Mbps (compressed) ⁶ , 100 Gbps to 1 Tbps (raw) ⁷
Frame delay	< 50–100 ms end-to-end latency and <15 ms motion-to-photon latency ⁸⁹

Table 8. Holoportation KPIs

6.6.2.1 Normalization Formulas

To consistently evaluate performance, each metric is normalized on a 0 to 1 scale, where 1 signifies ideal performance and 0 indicates below acceptable thresholds. OpenTelemetry’s Metrics API collects this real-time data, which is processed as follows:

1. Normalized FPS (N_fps)

- In base of the following formula:

$$N_{fps} = \frac{fps - FPS_{min}}{FPS_{ideal} - FPS_{min}}$$

Equation 1. Normalized FPS (N_fps)

- We can substitute the values to:

$$N_{fps} = \frac{fps - 30}{60 - 30}$$

If fps is below 30, N_{fps} is set to 0. This measurement is crucial for assessing the visual fluidity and realism of the holoportation.

2. Normalized Latency (N_throughput)

- In base of the following formula:

⁶ “Microsoft holoportation. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/holoportation-3/>,” Accessed: 5 Feb. 2023.

⁷ X. Xu, Y. Pan, P. P. M. Y. Lwin, and X. Liang, “3d holographic display and its data transmission requirement,” in International Conference on Information Photonics and Optical Communications, Oct 2011, pp. 1–4

⁸T. Rhee, et al., “Augmented virtual teleportation for high-fidelity telecollaboration,” IEEE Trans. Vis. Comput. Graph. 2020, 26, 1923–1933

⁹ Hatim Chergui, Adriana Fernandez, “6GENABLERS-E2.1 Use Case Definition Report”, 2023.

$$N_{\text{throughput}} = \frac{\text{throughput} - \text{Throughput}_{\text{min}}}{\text{Throughput}_{\text{ideal}} - \text{Throughput}_{\text{min}}}$$

Equation 2. Normalized Latency (N_throughput)

- We can substitute the values to:

$$N_{\text{throughput}} = \frac{\text{throughput} - 30 \text{ Mbps}}{100 \text{ Gbps} - 30 \text{ Mbps}}$$

This ensures that throughput measurements are scaled to reflect effective high-resolution data transmission capabilities.

3. Normalized Throughput (N_delay)

- In base of the following formula:

$$N_{\text{delay}} = 1 - \frac{\text{delay} - \text{Delay}_{\text{ideal}}}{\text{Delay}_{\text{max}} - \text{Delay}_{\text{ideal}}}$$

Equation 3. Normalized Throughput (N_delay)

- We can substitute the values to:

$$N_{\text{delay}} = 1 - \frac{\text{delay} - 15 \text{ ms}}{100 \text{ ms} - 15 \text{ ms}}$$

Delays exceeding 100 ms result in N_{delay} being set to 0, emphasizing the importance of ultra-low latency for real-time interactions.

Quality of Service (QoS) Index Calculation

The composite QoS index combines these normalized metrics to provide a comprehensive view of service quality. The formula for the QoS index, incorporating weighted averages of these metrics, is:

- **Weights:**
 - $w_{\text{fps}}=0.2$
 - $w_{\text{throughput}}=0.5$
 - $w_{\text{latency}}=0.3$

Holoportation KPIs Ranges

The final formula for QoS is:

$$QoS = w_{fps} \times N_{fps} + w_{throughput} \times N_{throughput} + w_{delay} \times N_{delay}$$

Equation 4. Final formula for QoS

6.6.2.2 Representation of the values

Here are the graphs representing the normalized values of key performance indicators (KPIs) for holoportation based on the OpenTelemetry metrics:

1. **Normalized Frame per Second (FPS)** - Shows how the FPS values are normalized on a scale from 0 to 1, where 1 represents the ideal frame rate (60 FPS) and values below 30 FPS are considered unacceptable (set to 0).

Figure 10. Normalized Frame per Second (FPS)

2. **Normalized Server-side Perceived Throughput** - Illustrates the normalization of throughput measurements. The graph normalizes these values from the minimum acceptable for compressed data (30 Mbps) up to the ideal for raw data (100 Gbps), indicating that higher throughput significantly enhances the holoportation experience.

Figure 11. Normalized Server-side Perceived Throughput

3. **Normalized Frame Delay** - Displays the delay in transmitting frames, normalized such that values less than 15 ms are ideal and delays beyond 100 ms are unacceptable, scaled inversely to reflect the increased impact of higher delays on the user experience.

Figure 12. Normalized Frame Delay

Here is the table that outlines the data used for the normalized graphs of each key performance indicator (KPI) for holoportation:

KPI	Description	Range	Normalized Calculation	Value
Frame per Second (FPS)	Measures the number of frames processed per second.	> 30 FPS	$N_{fps} = \frac{fps-30}{30}$ if $fps \geq 30$, otherwise 0	
Server-side Perceived Throughput	Amount of data processed per second.	30 to 50 Mbps (compressed), 100 Gbps to 1 Tbps (raw)	$N_{throughput} = \frac{throughput - 30 \text{ Mbps}}{1 \text{ Tbps} - 30 \text{ Mbps}}$	
Frame Delay	Time taken for a frame to be delivered end-to-end.	< 50–100 ms end-to-end latency, < 15 ms motion-to-photon latency	$N_{delay} = 1 - \frac{delay - 15 \text{ ms}}{85 \text{ ms}}$ if $delay \leq 100 \text{ ms}$, otherwise 0	

Table 9. Normalized graph data

6.6.3 Another relevant metrics

This table details supplementary telemetry metrics that are crucial for maintaining the operational integrity and performance of the holoportation system. Each metric is collected and analyzed using specific instruments provided by OpenTelemetry, which facilitate real-time monitoring and prompt responsiveness to system dynamics.

Metric	Instrument	Description	Application
Frame Transfer Delay	Histogram	Time taken for a frame to be transferred from one point to another.	Monitors transfer speeds and alerts for any delays.
Sensor Data Latency	Histogram	Time taken by each sensor's data to be processed.	Monitors latency across all sensors and alerts for any delays.
Encoding Delay	Histogram	Time taken to encode a specific volume of video data.	Monitors encoding speeds and alerts for any delays.
Packet Delivery Rate	Counter	Number of packets successfully reaching the destination.	Monitors successful data deliveries ensuring integrity.
Bandwidth Utilization	Gauge	Measures the amount of used bandwidth versus available bandwidth.	Monitors network efficiency and helps optimize data flow.
Errors	Counter	Number of errors between components or in third parties' communication or APIs request/responses	Ensures integrity and prompts action when this occurs.

CPU Utilization	Gauge	Percentage of CPU being used.	Identifies CPU usage patterns and potential bottlenecks.
Memory Usage	Gauge	Memory being consumed by processes.	Monitors for potential memory leaks or overutilization.

Table 10. OpenTelemetry Relevant Metrics

6.6.4 Implementation and Real-Time Monitoring

Using OpenTelemetry, real-time data is continuously streamed into an analytics dashboard. This tool allows network operators to dynamically monitor and adjust system parameters to ensure the holoportation system consistently operates at peak performance levels.

6.6.5 Conclusion

This quantitative approach allows network operators and system engineers to objectively assess the performance of holoportation services. By setting rigorous standards and continuously monitoring these key metrics, we can ensure that the service not only meets but exceeds the high expectations set for 6G network capabilities, thus enhancing user satisfaction and service reliability.

7. Comparative Design Analysis

7.1 Overview of Considered Design Alternatives

In the development of the high-precision telemetry enablement for 6G networks, several design alternatives were evaluated, including the integration of advanced in-band network telemetry (INT) as explored by Velasco et al. (2023).¹⁰ While our final design does not incorporate pervasive monitoring and distributed intelligence strategies detailed in their work, these approaches represent a valuable future enhancement for achieving scalable near real-time operations across 6G networks. Their model suggests employing intelligent data aggregation and distributed control, which could potentially address scalability issues related to massive data collection and processing demands inherent in 6G environments. These concepts were critically considered, providing a contrasting framework that helped refine the decisions in our selected architecture, which emphasizes real-time data processing with Telegraf and InfluxDB.

7.2 Comparative Analysis of Alternative Designs vs. the Chosen Design

1. Centralized Telemetry Architecture:

- **Pros:** Simplifies management by centralizing data processing and analysis. This can enhance data security and make it easier to implement comprehensive updates and maintenance.
- **Cons:** Potential bottlenecks and single points of failure, which can degrade performance as network size and data volume expand. High latency in data processing due to the central aggregation of data.
- **Performance Metrics:** Centralized systems often struggle with latency issues as they scale, particularly in environments expecting real-time data processing, like those required for 5G and 6G networks.

2. Distributed Telemetry Architecture:

- **Pros:** Reduces latency by processing data close to its source, supports real-time decision-making, and enhances system resilience and fault tolerance by eliminating single points of failure.
- **Cons:** Can be complex to manage due to its decentralized nature. Consistency and synchronization across nodes become challenging as the number of nodes increases.
- **Performance Metrics:** Offers reduced data transmission times and quicker response rates, essential for the latency-sensitive applications expected in 6G networks.

¹⁰ L. Velasco, M. Ruiz, P. Gonzalez, F. Paolucci, A. Sgambelluri, and C. Papagianni, "Pervasive Monitoring and Distributed Intelligence for 6G Near Real-Time Operation." Zenodo, 2023.

3. Hierarchical Telemetry Architecture:

- **Pros:** Combines elements of both centralized and distributed architectures, aiming to optimize resource utilization and reduce latency by localizing data processing.
- **Cons:** The complexity of managing multiple layers can introduce overhead and potential delays in escalation and response times during anomalies.
- **Performance Metrics:** Provides a balanced approach but may not fully meet the ultra-low latency requirements for certain 6G applications without significant optimization.¹¹

7.3 Justification for the Selection of the Final Design

Component	Centralized Architecture	Distributed Architecture	Hierarchical Architecture	Final Hybrid Design	Justification for Chosen Design
Data Collection	Centralized data hubs	Edge-based collection	Layered data aggregation	Advanced, protocol-specific collection	The chosen design uses protocol-specific collectors to minimize latency and maximize efficiency, adapting better to the diverse and high-speed data streams of 6G networks.
Data Processing	Central processing units	Local processing at nodes	Mixed central and local processing	Real-time processing with Telegraf and InfluxDB	Real-time processing capabilities are critical for 6G applications, allowing the system to handle high data rates and provide immediate responses.
Analytics Services	Standard analytics	AI-driven local analytics	Mixed model analytics	Specialized analytics tailored for 6G needs	Specialized analytics provide deep insights into network performance and user experience, crucial for optimizing 6G services.
Feature Services	Basic feature extraction	Dynamic feature extraction at edge	Hierarchical feature management	Enhanced feature management using Feast	Enhanced features with real-time processing capabilities are essential for handling the variability and volume of 6G data.
Alarm Services	Centralized alarms	Distributed alarm triggers	Mixed alarm management	Integrated with TM Forum's Alarm API	Integrating TM Forum's API facilitates proactive network management, crucial for maintaining 6G reliability and minimizing

¹¹ González Pacheco P. Real Time Control for Intelligent 6G Networks. 2023. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/2117/394841>. Accessed April 17, 2024.

					downtime.
Network Management	Manual adjustments based on aggregated data	Automated local adjustments	Mixed centralized and edge management	Automated management using continuous telemetry data	Automation enhances network responsiveness and efficiency, reducing latency and administrative overhead in 6G networks.
User Interfaces	Static dashboards	Customizable per-node UIs	Hierarchical control panels	Dynamic interfaces with Grafana, Prometheus, Jaeger	Dynamic UIs improve user interaction and operational monitoring, aligning with the needs of sophisticated 6G environments.
Scalability	Limited by central capacity	High scalability at node level	Scalable with hierarchical control	Highly scalable with intelligent data flow management	The final design's scalable approach ensures the system can accommodate the expansive scale and dynamic conditions of 6G networks efficiently.

Table 11. Justification for the Selection of the Final Design

The final hybrid design was selected for its superior ability to balance scalability, real-time data processing capabilities, and intelligent analytics, which are pivotal for meeting the operational demands of emerging 6G networks. This design merges the best features of centralized, distributed, and hierarchical architectures, optimizing for both performance and management:

- **Real-time Data Processing:** The final design incorporates real-time data processing with Telegraf and InfluxDB, crucial for handling the high data rates and immediate response requirements of 6G networks.
- **Specialized Analytics:** By using advanced analytics tailored to specific performance, QoS, and UX demands, the final design optimizes network operations and enhances user satisfaction.
- **Integrated Alarm Services:** The use of TM Forum's Alarm API allows for sophisticated fault detection and management, which is key for maintaining 6G network uptime and reliability.
- **Interactive User Interfaces:** The shift to dynamic and interactive UIs with Grafana, Prometheus, and Jaeger supports better visualization and quicker response times, aligning with the interactive nature of 6G services.

7.4 Additional Considerations

- **Alternative designs** were considered, including more modular feature services and cloud-based alarm systems. These were chosen having in count the need for real-time processing and local data handling capabilities crucial for 6G's low-latency requirements.

- The final design optimally balances between scalability, real-time capabilities, and intelligent analytics, which were identified as key for the operational demands of emerging 6G networks.

8.State of the Art and Technological Advancements

8.1 Current Technologies and Methodologies in High-Precision Telemetry

High-precision telemetry has seen some advancements driven by the need for real-time, accurate, and comprehensive monitoring and management of network systems. The exploration of 6G communications, as discussed in the paper work by Akash Agarwal¹², presents a comprehensive vision for the future where digital, physical, and biological systems are seamlessly integrated. This visionary landscape is where our design principles find their grounding, aiming to facilitate the seamless operation and integration of telemetry in advanced mobile networks. In base of the current state-of-the-art, some of the technologies include:

1. **OpenTelemetry**: An observability framework that provides APIs and tools for capturing and exporting telemetry data (metrics, logs, traces) in a standardized format. Its widespread adoption has set a high benchmark for observability in cloud-native environments.
2. **InfluxDB**: A time-series database optimized for fast, high-availability storage and retrieval of time-stamped data, which is crucial for performance monitoring and event logging in real-time systems.
3. **Telegraf**: An agent for collecting, processing, and writing metrics, which is highly configurable and supports a variety of plugins that allow it to gather metrics from a diverse set of sources.
4. **Data Fusion Technologies**: These are increasingly being utilized to aggregate data from multiple sources to create a unified view of information, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of the derived insights.
5. **Advanced Machine Learning Models**: Leveraging machine learning for predictive analytics and intelligent decision-making has become a norm in enhancing the capabilities of network management systems.

In addition, a recent study by Rzym et al. (2024)¹³, offers a compelling look at the potential of combining dynamic telemetry with deep neural networks to automate anomaly detection in 6G software-defined networks. This approach, which involves dynamically adjusting data collection intervals based on detected anomalies, provides a nuanced method to enhance network responsiveness and reliability. Such dynamic adaptations are particularly relevant to our goals, suggesting potential pathways for

¹² Agarwal, A. (2024). State-of-the-Art and Development of 6G Communications. In: Verma, O.P., Wang, L., Kumar, R., Yadav, A. (eds) Machine Intelligence for Research and Innovations. MAITRI 2023. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 831. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-8135-9_21

¹³ Rzym, G.; Masny, A.; Chołda, P. Dynamic Telemetry and Deep Neural Networks for Anomaly Detection in 6G Software-Defined Networks. *Electronics* **2024**, *13*, 382. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics13020382>

incorporating real-time, adaptive anomaly detection capabilities into our telemetry system.

8.2 Explanation of How the Final Design Advances the State of the Art

The final design of the high-precision telemetry enablement for 6G networks integrates and builds upon these technologies to create a sophisticated system that not only meets but exceeds current standards:

- **Integration of Real-Time Data Processing Technologies:** By integrating Telegraf and InfluxDB within the telemetry processing pipeline, the final design significantly enhances the system's ability to process and analyze data in real-time. This reduces latency in decision-making from minutes to milliseconds, a critical improvement for 6G networks where speed is paramount.
- **Enhanced Data Fusion Capabilities:** The final design incorporates a Telemetry Fusion Hub that aggregates data from various sources before it was validated and feature extraction. This ensures that data coherence is maintained, enhancing the reliability of the analytics derived from this data.
- **Advanced Feature Services with Machine Learning Readiness:** Utilizing Feast, Redis, and PostgreSQL for feature extraction and management allows the system to support sophisticated machine learning applications and adaptive systems efficiently. This represents an advance in managing the lifecycle of data features and ensuring that machine learning models are fed with high-quality, relevant data.
- **Scalable and Modular Architecture:** The system's architecture, built on Kubernetes, offers high scalability and modularity, allowing for easy adaptation to changing network demands and technologies without extensive overhauls.

8.3 Contributions to the Field of 6G Network Technologies

The final design contributes to the field of 6G network technologies in several significant ways:

1. **Enabling Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC):** The ability to process and analyze data in real-time is fundamental to URLLC in 6G networks.
2. **Supporting Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC):** Integrating scalable solutions that can handle vast amounts of data from potentially millions of devices, the final design is well-suited to support mMTC.
3. **Facilitating Network Slicing:** The modular and flexible architecture allows for tailored analytics and monitoring for various virtual networks, which is crucial for the effective implementation of network slicing—a core feature of 6G.

4. **Advancing Edge Computing:** By processing data locally at the edge of the network before it is aggregated and analyzed centrally, the design optimizes resource usage and reduces response times.

In summary, the final design of the high-precision telemetry enablement system for 6G networks sets a new benchmark in the field. It advances the state of the art by integrating cutting-edge technologies and methodologies to create a robust, scalable, and efficient system capable of meeting the complex demands of next-generation networks. This design not only enhances current capabilities but also provides a foundation for future innovations in the rapidly evolving landscape of network technologies.

9. System Integration and Operational Dynamics

9.1 Overview

The final design of the high-precision telemetry enablement for 6G networks is an orchestration of various components, each oriented to the system's overall performance and efficiency. This section delves into the interactions between these components and examines the dependencies that are crucial for the seamless operation of the system. The architecture's design not only facilitates robust intra-system communications but also ensures compatibility with external systems, reinforcing its adaptability and scalability in dynamic network environments.

9.2 Component Interactions

The telemetry system is structured to optimize data flow from collection to analysis, ensuring that each component contributes effectively to the network's telemetry and analytic capabilities. Here is how the components interact within the system:

1. Data Collection to Processing:

- **Edge Devices and Sensors** initiate the data collection process, capturing raw telemetry data which is then transmitted to the **OpenTelemetry Collector**.
- The **OpenTelemetry Collector** acts as the primary entry point, normalizing and forwarding the data to **Telegraf** for further processing.
- **Telegraf** processes this data, adhering to protocols suitable for **InfluxDB** integration, ensuring that the data is formatted for efficient time-series data storage.

2. Data Analysis and Storage:

- Once in **InfluxDB**, the data becomes available for both real-time and historical analysis.
- The **Telemetry Fusion Hub** aggregates this data, ensuring its coherence before it is sent to the **Centralized Collector Hub** for validation.
- Post-validation, the data is directed towards **Feature Services** and **Analytics Services** for detailed analysis.

3. Analytics and Decision Making:

- **Feature Services** extract relevant features from the data using tools like Feast, which are stored in Redis for real-time access or in PostgreSQL for batch processing.

- **Analytics Services** then take over, utilizing the processed data to generate actionable insights, which are crucial for business applications and operational decisions.

4. **User Interface and External Integration:**

- Insights and analytics are visualized through **User Interfaces** such as Grafana, Prometheus, and Jaeger, providing real-time network health and performance monitoring.
- External APIs like the **TM Forum QoS and Alarm APIs** integrate with the Analytics Services to enhance quality service management and alarm management, facilitating proactive network maintenance.

9.3 System Dependencies

The final design's functionality relies heavily on both internal and external dependencies:

1. **Internal Dependencies:**

- **Data Integrity:** The system's accuracy is heavily dependent on the integrity of data collected from edge devices. The Telemetry Fusion Hub and Centralized Collector Hub play critical roles in ensuring data coherence and validation before it progresses to feature extraction and analysis.
- **Component Synchronization:** Seamless operation requires meticulous synchronization between the OpenTelemetry Collector, Telegraf, and InfluxDB to handle data spikes and ensure continuous data flow without loss.

2. **External Dependencies:**

- **Cloud Services and Infrastructure:** The system depends on external cloud services for additional computational power and data storage capabilities, particularly for handling extensive data loads generated by 6G networks.
- **Standardization Bodies:** Compliance with standards set by entities like TM Forum ensures that the system aligns with industry best practices for performance management and service quality, facilitating interoperability with other 6G network components.

The interaction between these components is visually represented in the following flowchart, which illustrates the data's journey from initial collection to final analytic output, encapsulating the robust integration and seamless data handling processes integral to the system. This is represented in Figure 13:

Figure 13. System Dependencies

9.4 Conclusion

The final design of the telemetry system for 6G networks is an integration of various technologies working together focusing into be a great solution for the next generation networks. This interconnected and interdependent architecture tries to set a foundation for future advancements, ensuring that the system remains adaptable and scalable in the face of evolving network technologies and requirements. By detailing the interactions and dependencies of its components, the system promises robust performance, enhanced reliability, and exceptional service quality in the dynamic landscape of 6G networking.

10. Concluding Remarks

This document has delineated the comprehensive design and implementation of a high-precision telemetry system tailored for the emerging demands of 6G networks. This final design represents the culmination of rigorous research, extensive design iterations, and meticulous integration of cutting-edge technologies, all conducted under the ideas and objectives of the 6GENABLERS project. By advancing beyond the initial prototypes and integrating data processing frameworks, the system sets a new benchmark in network telemetry, offering capabilities essential for the next generation of mobile communications.

The design choices and modifications outlined herein have been driven by a clear objective to optimize telemetry accuracy and efficiency, essential for the robust requirements of 6G infrastructures. Through detailed comparative analyses, the chosen design has been validated against several alternatives, establishing its superiority in terms of scalability, real-time data processing, and system integration. The architecture is compliance with the current state-of-the-art, in the context of telemetry for advanced network systems.

Furthermore, the interactions and dependencies between various system components have been explicated to demonstrate the cohesive and integrated nature of the final design. This system is not an isolated set of technologies but a synergistic assembly that ensures seamless operation and high reliability under the dynamic conditions expected in 6G networks. The reliance on both established standards and innovative technologies facilitates a robust platform capable of adapting to future advancements and scaling according to evolving network demands.

In conclusion, the high-precision telemetry system designed through this project is poised to significantly enhance the operational capabilities of 6G networks. It will provide network operators with unprecedented insight and control over their infrastructures, thereby enhancing performance, reliability, and user satisfaction. As 6G technology continues to evolve, the flexibility and scalability of this telemetry system ensure that it will continue being useful for network management, offering a resilient and adaptive solution for the future.

This project marks a significant milestone in telemetry development and establishes a foundational platform for ongoing innovation in the field of network technologies. The insights gained and the technologies developed through this initiative are expected to inform and inspire continued advancements, driving the next waves of changes in how we understand and manage ultra-high-speed, high-density, and highly reliable network environments.